

Coordination Across the Data-to-Decision Pipeline

Project team: Carly Hansen*, Vincent Tidwell‡, Faisal Ashraf*, Brittany Davis‡, Christopher DeRolph*, Amelia Green €, Natalie Griffiths*, Shih-Chieh Kao*, Sara Larsen €, Kyle Larson‡, Maruti Mudunuru‡, Kyle Onda €, Esther Parish*, Debjani Singh*, Faith Sternlieb €, Sean Turner*, Nathalie Voisin‡, Andrew White‡

* Oak Ridge National Laboratory

‡ Pacific Northwest National Laboratory

€ Internet of Water Coalition

To build watershed intelligence, technological solutions must be networked across the full spectrum of physical and digital infrastructure that are involved in data collection/creation, informatics, and modeling or analysis to support decision making and include relevant voices in each stage of the process. This requires coordination across the numerous entities who are actively working towards solutions at each stage. Rather than having each agency develop a stove-piped data-to-decision pathway, coordination across pathways will lead to better operational decisions and improved efficiencies.

GAPS

From discussions with stakeholders during Phases 1 and 2, it is clear that there has been significant technology deployment to support watershed science and resource management in the U.S. However, watershed intelligence is more than technology deployment. Intelligence requires the technology to be connected across disparate platforms (e.g., sensing, databases, models) and coordinated among the numerous entities managing the watershed. Where operational examples of well-integrated technological solutions were cited, applications tended to be limited to specific users, use cases, or geographies. This broad coordination hurdle can be attributed to two ubiquitous challenges:

- **A large number of agents and disparity in decisional objectives.** Management of watershed resources is broadly distributed across numerous agencies. A few examples include water and reservoir operations-USBR and/or USACE; water quality-EPA; environment-U.S. Fish and Wildlife; agriculture-USDA; hydropower-utilities. Watersheds are also crisscrossed by multiple jurisdictional boundaries including private landowners, cities, utilities, counties, states, and federal agencies. In this way, each agent is faced with a unique set of operational/management decisions. This has required them to develop data-to-decision pipelines tailored to the agent's specific needs—unique in terms of data requirements, decision analytics, and the spatial and temporal resolution.
- **Funding.** Discussions about the obstacles facing adoption of technological solutions repeatedly centered around common government funding constraints. Part of the problem is that funding for sampling, databases, and modeling must flow through individual agencies. As priorities often differ across agencies, coordination of funding for joint ventures takes extra work. Funding is also driven by administration and agency priorities and thus is subject to change. While funds are often available to develop new technologies, databases, or models, maintaining long-term support is difficult. These challenges escalate when trying to establish long-term, cross-agency support for coordinated data-to-decision pipelines.

In engagements with experts to support this roadmap, conversations largely centered around government and not-for-profit private-funding challenges. However, experts familiar with private sector perspectives described growing appetites from businesses and capital investment firms to

better represent water and energy systems and translate existing research to non-technical audiences so they can make decisions about development and mitigating risks.

While the gap is limited coordination across the data-to-decision pipeline, the result is reduced efficiency and efficacy in the decision process. Inefficiency is evidenced largely through the duplication of efforts, which occurs when each agent individually searches for data; downloads, cleans, and prepares data for modeling; develops modeling workflows to rectify, scale and grid/network the data; develops and calibrates their own model; and performs scenario/uncertainty analysis.

EMERGING SOLUTIONS

While gaps in coordination exist, this does not mean that coordination is absent. In fact, considerable strides have been made in cross-agency coordination; however, many opportunities still exist to improve coordination and hence advance watershed intelligence. Below are a few examples that address different aspects of coordination across the entire data-to-decision spectrum.

Table 1. Exemplary coordination across the data-to-decision spectrum

Portion of the data-to-decision spectrum	Summary of emerging solutions	Examples of watershed-scale, multi-agency, -sector, and -disciplinary coordination
Data collection	<p>Largely focused on sensing and determining the best combination of ground-based measurements with remote-sensing technologies for a range of different environmental conditions.</p> <p>Increasingly, coordination is extending beyond sensor development and is motivated by gaining a better understanding of the governing physics and formulation of effective analytical models, while creating accessible and understandable data services.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • USGS: Next Generation Water Observing System • NASA: SnowEx • DOE: SAIL/East River Project • Weather Underground: Personal Weather Station Network (PWS) <p>It is worth noting that coordination in collecting information with different technologies is happening primarily within the bounds of each agency, while informal coordination occurs between agency researchers.</p>
Informatics	<p>Many solutions addressing information discoverability and use are related to increasing and broadening participation in the decision-making process from various stakeholders.</p> <p>Both sharing and access/capacity-building solutions are involved in improving the ability to visualize, manipulate, and use a broad set of data types to support analysis.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NOAA: National Snow and Ice Data Center, and the Exchange for Observations and Local Knowledge of the Arctic (ELOKA) • NSF: Open Knowledge Network • CUAHSI: HydroShare and HydroClient • Internet of Water: GeoConnex <p>These examples of data sharing platforms exemplify coordination because they are not limited to</p>

		information produced by a single agency.
Modeling	<p>Increased coordination in modeling has led to improved development, maintenance, and broader application of models.</p> <p>Benefits from emerging efforts are seen in the distribution of costs across collaborators; expanded expertise contributing to the model; rigorous testing and vetting through repeated use of a particular tool; elevated exposure and improved name recognition; and creation of shared modeling infrastructure from personnel to generalizable workflows.</p>	<p>Coordination across a particular regional model: water managers in the Colorado River Basin coordinate around the Colorado River Simulation System. Notably, the USBR released the Post-2026 Operations Explorations Web Tool to allow stakeholders who are external to USBR to develop and test operational alternatives. Communities forming around a sophisticated modeling platform:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • USGS: developed the Modular Hydrologic Model (MODFLOW). Members of the community have created specialized sub-routines and modeling interfaces. • NCAR: Community Climate Model, an open global atmosphere model that has received numerous contributions from federal agencies and academia. Over 40 years, it has evolved into a complete earth system model with land, ice, and ocean components. <p>Model-agnostic communities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NWS Office of Water Prediction: The Next Generation Water Resources Modeling Framework (NextGen). See Section 3.3.1 <i>Forecasting</i>

Another critical piece of the conversation around coordination is the question of “coordination to what end?”. When researchers/practitioners come together to solve a particular problem, they can create a **Community of Practice** (CoP). The idea is to create a shared space that fosters enhanced communication, knowledge transfer, sharing of data/tools, expanded networking, ideation, and collaboration around a common interest. Efficacy benefits are realized when the same datasets, workflows, and models are subjected to the rigors of use by different agents. Less duplication of effort frees staff time to devote to process improvement. Also of importance is the fact that decision making is based on a shared set of information and tools—everyone is working from the same set of information.

A particular example is the [Multi-Sector Dynamics CoP \(MSD\)](#). The MSD CoP aims to improve understanding of human and natural systems and build tools that cross sectors and scales. Coordination is accomplished through the CoP in several ways. A shared knowledge base, [MSD-LIVE](#), includes a data and code repository, computational notebooks for visualizing data, and project/team management tools to facilitate collaboration. Community coordination is also reinforced through the development of a roadmap and other founding documents, hosted webinar series, regular virtual group and subgroup meetings, publication of a newsletter, deliberate mentoring of junior staff, organized sessions at leading conferences, and arrangement of special sessions in related journals. Here, seed funding through DOE's Office of Science was necessary to nucleate a team and standup MSD-LIVE, while broader participation is completely voluntary.

An example of a CoP implemented within a particular agency is the USACE [Planning Community of Practice \(PCoP\)](#). It helps to share tools, training, and resources across various districts divisions, and research laboratories. The PCoP consists of several sub-CoPs with even more specific focus areas, from preserving and protecting tribal cultural resources, conducting economic analysis of design and implementation of water resources projects, planning support, to ecosystem restoration. Many of the resources supporting the PCoP and its sub-CoPs are shared through bi-weekly webinars and then made available online. The PCoP emphasizes job training and development, curating guides for certification programs, maintaining a database of planners in each district, and conducts annual workshops to help USACE staff understand and implement technical assistance programs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Create Community of Practices

- Create a Community of Practice around key hydropower topics that integrate industry needs and experience and current research. Examples of broad topics where industry experience complements R&D include: development and retrofit of existing infrastructure or hydropower operations under extreme and variable climate conditions. Greater experience and knowledge sharing among experts in practice and in research can help calibrate R&D efforts as well as increase awareness and use of existing data or resources.
- Additionally, a Community of Practice across federal agencies to coordinate joint efforts toward realizing Intelligent Watersheds could extend beyond hydropower interests. The data-to-decision pipeline used throughout this roadmap offers a logical organizing structure around which experts can engage and share information.

Support a cross-agency knowledge base for dam, reservoir, operations, and hydropower data

- Building on National Reservoir Data Symposium, Feb. 21-23, 2024. Establish cross-agency task force and/or fund National Academies study of opportunities to manage long-term funding of legacy knowledge bases.

Establish inter-agency coordination team on IW

- Create an inter-agency team to address issues governing the efficient coordination of information flow and decision-making at watershed scales. The team would include representatives from related federal, state and local watershed management agencies. The team would coordinate research, resource deployment, and funding issues that crosscut jurisdictional boundaries.

Explore opportunities for public-private support of research

- Those managing complicated supply chains, dealing with international or regional markets, or making major capital investment decisions require information about risks to water and energy resources. Finding avenues where research can be supported by both public and private interests may lead to the types of granularity and metrics that are meaningful for making critical business and development related decisions within the private sector